

Analyzing Overlapping Communities in Heterogeneous Information Networks with Self-Supervised HGNN and Fuzzy C-Means

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Abstract. We study overlapping community detection in heterogeneous information networks (HINs) by combining self-supervised heterogeneous graph neural networks (HGNNs) with fuzzy clustering. Existing self-supervised HGNNs, such as HeCo, are typically evaluated on single-label tasks (node classification, link prediction) and rely on hard clustering (e.g., K-means), which forces each node into exactly one community. This setting is misaligned with real networks, where nodes often belong to multiple communities.

We propose a framework that uses a HeCo-style front-end to learn two views of node representations on HINs—schema view and meta-path view—and then applies Fuzzy C-means (FCM) to obtain fuzzy community memberships. To better exploit multi-view information, we standardize each view separately before concatenation, preventing one view from dominating the distance computation in clustering. We analyze not only standard clustering metrics (NMI, ARI) but also the fuzzy partition coefficient (FPC) and the distributions of maximum and second-largest memberships.

Experiments on the DBLP heterogeneous bibliographic network show that schema-view embeddings significantly outperform raw features and meta-path-view embeddings in clustering accuracy, and that view-wise standardized concatenation further improves NMI while yielding more overlapping communities (lower FPC, lower max membership, higher second-largest membership). Our results demonstrate that combining self-supervised HGNN embeddings with FCM provides an effective and interpretable way to uncover overlapping community structure in HINs.

Keywords: Overlapping community detection · Heterogeneous information networks · Self-supervised heterogeneous graph neural networks · Multi-view representation learning · Fuzzy C-means clustering.

1 Introduction

In recent years, graph representation learning on heterogeneous information networks (HINs), which consist of multiple types of nodes and relations such as user–item and paper–author links, has been extensively studied[9, 11]. In particular, heterogeneous graph neural networks (HGNNs), which can handle multiple node and relation types, have shown promising results on various tasks such as recommendation, link prediction, and node classification[16, 12]. Moreover, since in real-world data only a small fraction of nodes are typically labeled, many methods have been proposed to learn general-purpose node embeddings via self-supervised learning that does not rely on labels. HeCo, one representative example, models a HIN from two perspectives—schema view and meta-path view—and demonstrates that high-quality node representations can be obtained through co-contrastive learning between these views[16, 7].

However, existing self-supervised HGNNs typically rely on hard clustering (e.g., K-means), ignoring the overlapping nature of real-world networks where nodes often belong to multiple communities (e.g., interdisciplinary authors)[17, 14, 6, 10, 13]. To address this limitation, we introduce Fuzzy C-means (FCM), which assigns continuous membership degrees to nodes, providing a natural relaxation of hard assignments[3, 8, 1]. While FCM handles ambiguity well, its combination with self-supervised HGNN embeddings remains underexplored.

To address this issue, we propose a framework for fuzzy (overlapping) community detection in heterogeneous graphs that uses a self-supervised HGNN as a front-end and applies Fuzzy C-means on top of its output embeddings. Specifically, we construct two types of embeddings—schema-view and meta-path-view embeddings based on HeCo—and integrate them into a multi-view embedding by standardizing the scale of each view and then concatenating them. We then apply FCM to this integrated embedding and estimate a cluster membership vector for each node, thereby obtaining multi-label-like community memberships for nodes. Furthermore, by analyzing the distributions of the maximum and second-largest elements of the membership vectors as well as the fuzzy partition coefficient (FPC), we quantitatively evaluate what kinds of structures are emphasized by the schema view, the meta-path view, and the integrated view, and what overlapping community structure emerges through view integration.

We evaluate our framework on the DBLP heterogeneous bibliographic network. By comparing our standardized multi-view embedding approach against single-view baselines and hard clustering methods, we demonstrate that our method achieves a superior balance between clustering performance and the detection of overlapping community structures.

2 Related Work

2.1 Self-supervised Heterogeneous Graph Neural Networks

As attempts to apply graph neural networks to heterogeneous information networks (HINs), numerous HGNNs that explicitly handle different node and re-

lation types have been proposed[9, 15, 5]. For example, some methods control information propagation between heterogeneous nodes by introducing relation-specific linear transformations or attention mechanisms, while others perform neighborhood aggregation based on meta-paths. These models have mainly been designed in supervised settings using labeled data, with the aim of improving the accuracy of node classification and link prediction.

However, in real-world HINs labeled nodes are often scarce, making label-independent representation learning crucial. To address this issue, many self-supervised HGNNs that combine self-supervised learning with contrastive learning have recently been proposed[16, 7, 12]. Representative methods like HeCo employ co-contrastive learning across multiple views to learn node embeddings without labels. Such self-supervised HGNNs have been evaluated mainly on tasks such as node classification, link prediction, and node clustering, and have been reported to exhibit good label efficiency and high versatility.

On the other hand, clustering evaluation in these methods typically assumes hard clustering using K-means, implicitly imposing the assumption that each node belongs to exactly one cluster. There has been insufficient discussion of how well the latent representations learned by self-supervised HGNNs reflect partial memberships in multiple communities, and how such overlapping structures should be extracted.

2.2 Clustering and Community Detection on HIN

Research on clustering and community detection on HINs aims to semantically partition sets of nodes by exploiting graph structure together with node and relation types[9, 11]. Traditionally, many studies have defined similarities using meta-paths or meta-graphs and then applied spectral clustering or matrix factorization to the resulting similarity matrices[11, 5]. Methods that optimize clustering objective functions defined on HINs, such as modularity or density measures, and approaches that estimate latent node clusters based on probabilistic generative models have also been proposed.

While these methods are useful in that they explicitly handle the heterogeneity of HINs, most of them assume that each node is assigned to exactly one cluster. In the context of community detection, there are models that deal with overlapping communities or overlapping clustering, but most of them target homogeneous graphs or bipartite graphs, and are difficult to directly apply to networks like HINs that have multiple node and edge types[17, 14, 6, 10, 13]. Moreover, systematic comparison and integration between recent HGNN-based methods and traditional HIN clustering approaches have not been sufficiently explored.

2.3 Fuzzy C-means and Overlapping Community Detection

A classical framework for handling overlapping communities and ambiguous cluster boundaries is Fuzzy C-means (FCM) clustering proposed by Bezdek[3, 8, 1]. FCM assigns continuous-valued memberships to each data point for each cluster

and minimizes an objective function under the constraint that these memberships sum to one. This relaxes the hard assumption adopted by K-means and similar methods—that each point belongs to exactly one cluster—and naturally represents situations in which a point partially belongs to multiple clusters.

While applied widely, its combination with self-supervised HGNNs remains limited[1, 10].

3 Proposed Framework

3.1 Overview of the Framework

The overall architecture of the proposed framework is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed framework

As input, we consider a heterogeneous information network $G = (V, E)$ with multiple node and edge types. Here we assume a bibliographic network such as DBLP, which includes node types such as authors, papers, terms, and venues (conferences/journals). Each node is assumed to be associated with an appropriate initial feature vector, such as a BoW representation of a paper or features derived from an author’s publication history.

The proposed method consists of three main stages. First, we learn two types of embeddings, $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ (schema) and $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$ (meta-path), using a self-supervised HGNN based on co-contrastive learning. Second, these embeddings are standardized and concatenated to form a multi-view embedding $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$, ensuring balanced contribution from both views. Finally, we apply Fuzzy C-means to these embeddings to estimate cluster membership vectors \mathbf{u}_i and analyze the overlapping community structures using metrics such as the Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC).

In this way, the framework has a two-stage structure: it first embeds the structure and attributes of a heterogeneous graph using a self-supervised HGNN, and then extracts fuzzy community structures on top of the embeddings via FCM.

3.2 Self-supervised HGNN Front-end (HeCo-based)

In this subsection, we describe the self-supervised HGNN front-end that constitutes the first stage of the proposed framework. In this study, we adopt a model that is simplified and restructured from the HeCo framework so that it is suitable for implementation on top of PyTorch Geometric[16].

Schema view GNN In the schema view, we treat the HIN as a single large graph with heterogeneous nodes and edges, and apply a GNN to the resulting heterograph that contains all edge types. We employ a heterogeneous GNN built with PyG’s HeteroConv and SAGEConv modules.

Concretely, for each node type t , the initial features $\mathbf{X}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_t \times d_t}$ are projected by a linear mapping into a shared hidden dimension d_{hid} , thereby aligning the dimensionality across types. We then apply SAGEConv for each edge type and aggregate messages from different edge types using HeteroConv to update the hidden representation of each node. By stacking this operation over multiple layers, we obtain author-node representations at the final layer, which we regard as the schema-view embeddings $\mathbf{z}^{(s)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times d}$.

Using SAGEConv allows us to perform message passing in a natural way even over bipartite edges such as author–paper or paper–term. Moreover, since all types are handled jointly, the schema view tends to form embeddings that capture the global structure of the entire HIN.

Meta-path view GNN In the meta-path view, we focus on specific meta-paths (sequences of node types) on the HIN, construct a “same-type node relation graph” corresponding to each meta-path, and apply a GNN to it. In this work, for author nodes in DBLP we use the following set of meta-paths:

- APA (Author–Paper–Author)
- APVPA (Author–Paper–Venue–Paper–Author)
- APTPA (Author–Paper–Term–Paper–Author)
- APAPA (Author–Paper–Author–Paper–Author)

For each meta-path, we construct the corresponding author–author meta-path adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times N_{\text{author}}}$ and apply a GCN-type GNN on it to obtain node embeddings. Specifically, for each meta-path we iteratively update the representations as in the following equation.

$$\mathbf{H}_{(l+1)}^{(m)} = \sigma \left(\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(m)} \mathbf{H}_{(l)}^{(m)} \mathbf{W}_l^{(m)} \right) \quad (1)$$

We treat the output of the final layer, $\mathbf{Z}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times d}$, as the author embedding in that meta-path. Where $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(m)}$ is the normalized meta-path adjacency matrix, and $\mathbf{H}_{(0)}^{(m)}$ is the initial author feature.

When there are multiple meta-paths, we follow the idea of HeCo and apply GNN to each meta-path separately, and then combine the resulting embeddings using cross-meta-path attention to obtain a single meta-path view embedding $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$. This allows us to implicitly learn which meta paths are important for which nodes.

Co-contrastive Learning between Views In self-supervised learning, co-contrastive learning is used to obtain a consistent representation of $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ and $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$ without labels. The basic idea is to minimize the InfoNCE-type contrast loss by treating the schema view embedding and meta-path view embedding of the same author node as positive examples, and embeddings of different authors as negative examples.

Specifically, we calculate the similarity matrix $\mathbf{S} = \tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}(\tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)})^\top$ from the L2-normalized embeddings $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)}$, and define the cross-entropy loss so that the diagonal elements (between the same nodes) are maximized. By averaging the losses in the two directions, schema \rightarrow meta and meta \rightarrow schema, a node representation that is consistent from both views is learned. In this self-supervised pretraining phase, we do not use any DBLP author labels.

3.3 Multi-view Embedding Integration

Through the self-supervised HGNN front-end, we obtain schema-view embeddings and meta-path-view embeddings for author nodes; in what follows, we explain how these two views are integrated and fed into fuzzy clustering.

View-wise Standardization One simple idea is to directly concatenate $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ and $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$:

$$\mathbf{z}_i^{(\text{concat})} = [\mathbf{z}_i^{(s)}; \mathbf{z}_i^{(m)}] \quad (2)$$

In practice, however, the scales and variances of the values in each view differ, so one view (e.g., the meta-path view) may dominate the Euclidean distance, causing the information from the other view to be effectively ignored.

To avoid this problem, we perform view-wise standardization before concatenating the embeddings. Concretely, for the embedding matrices $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ and $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$,

we standardize each feature dimension and obtain standardized embeddings $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)}$ as follows:

$$\hat{z}_{ik}^{(s)} = \frac{z_{ik}^{(s)} - \mu_k^{(s)}}{\sigma_k^{(s)}}, \quad \hat{z}_{ik}^{(m)} = \frac{z_{ik}^{(m)} - \mu_k^{(m)}}{\sigma_k^{(m)}}. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mu_k^{(s)}$ and $\sigma_k^{(s)}$ denote the mean and standard deviation of the k -th dimension of the schema-view embedding, and $\mu_k^{(m)}$ and $\sigma_k^{(m)}$ those of the meta-path-view embedding. Through this standardization, each view is rescaled to have zero mean and unit variance, enabling them to contribute fairly to subsequent distance computations.

Concatenation of Schema and Meta-path Views We then concatenate the standardized embeddings $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)}$ to construct the multi-view concatenated embedding $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$:

$$\mathbf{z}_i^{(\text{concat})} = [\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(s)}; \hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(m)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{d_s+d_m}. \quad (4)$$

In this setting, each dimension of $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$ has, overall, mean close to zero and standard deviation around one, so the schema and meta-path views are expected to contribute in a balanced way to Euclidean-distance calculations.

3.4 Fuzzy Community Detection via Fuzzy C-means

Finally, we describe the procedure for detecting fuzzy communities by applying Fuzzy C-means to the learned embeddings.

Fuzzy C-means Clustering Fuzzy C-means (FCM) is a clustering method that, given a predefined number of clusters C , simultaneously estimates the cluster centers $\{\mathbf{c}_j\}_{j=1}^C$ and the membership matrix $\mathbf{U} = [u_{ij}] \in [0, 1]^{N \times C}$ for data points $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^N$.

We minimize the standard FCM objective function with a fuzziness parameter m (set to 2.0) and number of clusters $C = 4$, subject to the constraint $\sum_{j=1}^C u_{ij} = 1$. To evaluate fuzziness, we employ the Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC), where a value closer to 1 indicates a hard partition and a value closer to $1/C$ indicates a highly fuzzy partition.

A value closer to 1 means that each data point belongs strongly to one cluster (close to hard), and a value closer to $1/C$ means that each data point belongs equally to all clusters (very fuzzy).

In addition, we analyze two distributions for each node i in this study.

1. Maximum membership value $\max_j u_{ij}$
2. Second maximum membership value

The maximum value $\max_j u_{ij}$ indicates how clearly a node has a primary cluster, while the second-largest value reflects how strongly it also belongs to a secondary cluster; in other words, it can be interpreted as an indicator of the degree of overlapping community membership. By comparing these distributions for the schema view, meta-path view, and concatenated view, we can clarify two aspects.

1. which view is closer to hard clustering.
2. which view better reflects multiple memberships in a “primary + secondary community” structure.

By combining the above components, the proposed framework integrates self-supervised HGNN-based embedding of heterogeneous graphs with fuzzy community detection, enabling overlapping community structures in heterogeneous networks to be analyzed in a quantitative and interpretable manner.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Dataset: DBLP Heterogeneous Network

For our experiments, we used the DBLP dataset, a representative heterogeneous bibliographic network[9, 2]. DBLP is a HIN composed of multiple node types—such as authors, papers, terms, and venues (conferences/journals)—and multiple types of edges connecting them.

We use the DBLP heterogeneous graph provided by PyTorch Geometric (PyG). This dataset includes four node types (author, paper, term, venue) and their corresponding edges (e.g., writes, published_in). We target the author nodes, which are labeled with four research areas.

In the PyG version of DBLP, the author, paper, and term nodes are each equipped with feature vectors $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$, whereas venue nodes have no features. Therefore, we attach a one-dimensional vector whose elements are 1 (or a one-hot vector) to venue nodes so that every node type has some feature representation.

Author nodes are annotated by DBLP with four research area labels (e.g., database, data mining, AI, information retrieval), and in this work we use these four areas as the number of clusters, fixing the number of clusters C to 4 in advance. The total number of author nodes is about 4,057, and we perform embedding learning and clustering on all of them.

4.2 Implementation Details

For the schema-view GNN, we use PyG’s HeteroConv and SAGEConv and apply a two-layer GNN to the heterograph that includes all edge types[4]. For each node type t , the initial features $\mathbf{X}^{(t)}$ are projected to a hidden dimension $d_{\text{hid}} = 64$ via a linear mapping, after which message passing is performed using SAGEConv. The output dimension of the final layer is also set to 64, and the outputs corresponding to author nodes are taken as the schema-view embeddings $\mathbf{z}^{(s)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times 64}$. We use ReLU as the activation function.

For the meta-path view, we construct adjacency matrices based on the four meta-paths defined in Section 3 (APA, APVPA, APTPA, APAPA).

First, we extract basic adjacency relations such as (author, writes, paper), (paper, published_in, venue), and (paper, has_term, term) from the PyG heterogeneous graph data and combine them via matrix multiplication to generate the above meta-path adjacency matrices as sparse matrices. For each meta-path, we apply a GCN-type layer to obtain author embeddings specific to that meta-path, and then integrate them using inter-meta-path attention (a simple weighted sum) to obtain the meta-path-view embeddings $\mathbf{z}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times 64}$.

For self-supervised learning, we use a co-contrastive loss on the embeddings of the schema and meta-path views. Specifically, we compute similarity matrices from the L2-normalized embeddings $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)}$ and use an InfoNCE-type loss to maximize the similarities of diagonal elements (the same author) in these matrices. We set the temperature parameter τ to 0.5. We use Adam as the optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-3} and a mini-batch size of 256 author nodes. The number of epochs for self-supervised pretraining is set to 50, during which no author labels are used.

Multi-view Embedding Integration After completing self-supervised pretraining, we store the schema-view embeddings $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ and meta-path-view embeddings $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$ for author nodes and use them in the clustering experiments.

When constructing the multi-view concatenated embedding $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$, we first standardize each view’s embedding dimension-wise. Concretely, using scikit-learn’s StandardScaler, we transform each dimension of $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$ and $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$ to have zero mean and unit variance, obtaining the standardized embeddings $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(s)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^{(m)}$. We then concatenate these in the dimensional direction to form a concatenated view embedding.

$$\mathbf{z}_i^{(\text{concat})} = [\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(s)}; \hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(m)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{128} \quad (5)$$

For comparison, we also calculated embeddings by directly concatenating the raw $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$, $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$ without standardizing them per view, and partially confirmed their behavior.

Fuzzy C-means and K-means For clustering, we used K-means, a representative hard clustering method, and Fuzzy C-means (FCM), a representative fuzzy clustering method. For K-means, we used the scikit-learn implementation, with the number of clusters $C = 4$, the number of initializations $n_{\text{init}} = 10$, and the random number seed fixed at 42.

For Fuzzy C-means, we use the cmeans function from scikit-fuzzy, setting the fuzziness parameter $m = 2.0$, the convergence threshold error to 10^{-5} , the maximum number of iterations maxiter to 1000, and the random seed to 42. As the data matrix, we use matrices in which rows correspond to author nodes and columns to feature dimensions for each embedding (raw features, $\mathbf{z}^{(s)}$, $\mathbf{z}^{(m)}$, and $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$), and we use the resulting membership matrix $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{author}} \times 4}$ and cluster centers \mathbf{c}_j for analysis.

4.3 Baselines and Settings

To verify the effectiveness of the proposed method, we set up the following baselines and comparison settings.

Baseline Methods We compare our method against three baselines: (1) K-means on raw features, (2) K-means/FCM on schema-view embeddings, and (3) K-means/FCM on meta-path-view embeddings. These comparisons allow us to evaluate the impact of self-supervised learning and view differences.

Proposed Multi-view Setting As our proposed method, we evaluate clustering on the standardized multi-view concatenated embedding: **Concat_std + K-means / FCM**

We apply K-means and FCM to the concatenated embedding $\mathbf{z}^{(\text{concat})}$ obtained after view-wise standardization and evaluate the clustering performance and fuzziness based on a representation that integrates information from both the schema and meta-path views. For comparison, in some experiments we also evaluate FCM on concatenated embeddings without standardization and confirm that view-wise standardization is important for multi-view integration.

Evaluation Metrics We evaluate performance using Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) and Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) for clustering accuracy, and the Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC) to assess the fuzziness of the resulting partitions.

In addition to FPC, we analyze the distributions for each author node i and evaluate differences in overlapping community structure across views.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Clustering Performance and Multi-view Integration

Table 1 summarizes the clustering performance across all settings.

First, the raw features yield poor results with both K-means and FCM, indicating limited consistency with the author labels. In contrast, embeddings learned by the self-supervised HGNN significantly improve performance. Specifically, the schema view outperforms the meta-path view in both NMI and ARI, capturing the global structure more effectively. Notably, the proposed standardized concatenated embedding (z_{concat}) achieves the best performance. When combined with K-means, it surpasses single-view baselines (NMI = 0.567, ARI = 0.574). Applying FCM further boosts these scores to the highest observed values (NMI = 0.590, ARI = 0.616). Regarding fuzziness, the FPC for the concatenated view (0.444) is lower than that of the single views (≈ 0.50), suggesting that multi-view integration forms a partition with stronger overlapping community structure. This demonstrates that our framework effectively balances high clustering accuracy with meaningful fuzziness, unlike the uninformative partition produced by raw features.

Table 1. Clustering performance comparison (NMI, ARI, FPC) across different representations and methods.

Representation	Clustering	NMI	ARI	FPC
Raw features	K-means	0.113	0.067	–
Raw features	FCM	0.015	0.015	0.250
Schema view (z_s)	K-means	0.471	0.466	–
Schema view (z_s)	FCM	0.535	0.572	0.495
Meta-path view (z_m)	K-means	0.367	0.287	–
Meta-path view (z_m)	FCM	0.468	0.485	0.501
Concat_std (z_{concat})	K-means	0.567	0.574	–
Concat_std (z_{concat})	FCM	0.590	0.616	0.444

5.2 Analysis of Fuzzy Membership

We closely analyze the differences among views by examining the distributions of the membership vectors obtained by Fuzzy C-means. Specifically, we compare (1) the distribution of the maximum membership values, (2) the distribution of the second-largest membership values, and (3) the FPC to evaluate how “hard” or “soft” the clustering formed by each view is.

Distribution of Max Membership Figure 2 shows the distributions of the maximum membership values $\max_j u_{ij}$ obtained from FCM for the schema view, meta-path view, and concat_std view. In addition, the means and standard deviations of $\max_j u_{ij}$ for each view are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Distributions of the maximum membership values obtained by Fuzzy C-means

For the schema view, the average maximum membership is around 0.7, indicating that many nodes belong relatively strongly to a single primary cluster. At

Table 2. Statistics of the maximum membership values and Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC).

View	Mean(Max)	Std(Max)	FPC
Schema	0.631	0.173	0.495
Meta-path	0.636	0.168	0.501
Concat_std	0.591	0.163	0.444

the same time, $FPC = 0.495$ is substantially smaller than 1, and the partition can be interpreted as having moderate fuzziness, where cluster boundaries are somewhat clear but memberships to secondary clusters still remain.

For the meta-path view, the distribution of maximum memberships is slightly shifted to higher values compared to the schema view, and FPC is also slightly larger at 0.501, suggesting that it forms a more hard-like partition that emphasizes local structures such as co-authorship or co-venue. However, its NMI and ARI are lower than those of the schema view, and thus its consistency with the field labels is inferior to that of the schema view.

On the other hand, for the standardized concatenated view, the maximum membership distribution of `concat_std` + FCM spreads to lower values than those of the schema and meta-path views, and its FPC is clearly smaller at 0.444. This means that the dominance of the primary cluster is somewhat weakened and memberships spanning multiple clusters become relatively stronger, suggesting that the `concat_std` embedding generates partitions that maintain meaningful cluster structure while exhibiting stronger overlapping community structure.

Distribution of Second Max Membership Furthermore, Figure 3 compares the distributions of the second-largest membership values obtained from FCM for the schema and meta-path views. The second-largest value can be interpreted as an indicator of how strongly a node belongs to a “secondary” cluster.

As can be seen from Figure 3, for both views the second-largest memberships are mostly distributed around 0.1–0.3, and there are very few nodes with values above 0.4. This indicates that many author nodes are structured such that they belong relatively strongly to one primary cluster while also having memberships of about 0.1–0.2 in another cluster.

Comparing the schema and meta-path views, the overall shapes of the distributions are very similar, but the meta-path view is slightly shifted toward smaller second-largest memberships, indicating a tendency for weaker memberships to non-primary clusters than in the schema view. This is consistent with the fact that the FPC values in Table 1 (0.495 and 0.501) are almost the same.

Taken together, the distribution of the second-largest memberships complements the analyses of the maximum memberships and FPC, and serves as an effective indicator for understanding how well each of the schema, meta-path, and `concat_std` views captures a “primary + secondary community” structure.

Fig. 3. Distributions of the second max membership values obtained by Fuzzy C-means

5.3 Summary of Findings

In summary, our results confirm that self-supervised HGNN embeddings far exceed raw features in clustering quality. While the schema view captures global structure better than the meta-path view, their standardized concatenation combined with FCM yields the best balance of high accuracy and meaningful fuzziness, effectively revealing overlapping communities.

These findings indicate that the proposed framework—combining embeddings obtained by a self-supervised HGNN on heterogeneous graphs with fuzzy clustering via Fuzzy C-means—can serve as a useful tool for quantitatively analyzing overlapping community structures that are difficult to capture with hard clustering alone.

6 Concluding Remarks

In this paper, we proposed a fuzzy community detection framework that combines a self-supervised heterogeneous graph neural network (HGNN) with Fuzzy C-means (FCM) for extracting overlapping community structures in heterogeneous information networks. Specifically, we adopt a self-supervised HGNN based on HeCo to learn two types of embeddings—the network schema view and the meta-path view—and construct a multi-view concatenated embedding by standardizing each view and then concatenating them. On top of these embeddings, we apply FCM and estimate cluster membership vectors for author nodes, thereby building a framework that explicitly represents their degrees of membership in multiple communities.

In experiments on the DBLP heterogeneous bibliographic network, we first confirmed the effectiveness of single-view embeddings learned by the self-supervised HGNN. While K-means on the raw features yielded low scores (NMI = 0.113, ARI = 0.067) and Raw features + FCM produced almost random and extremely

fuzzy partitions (NMI = 0.015, ARI = 0.015, FPC = 0.250), K-means on the schema-view embeddings achieved NMI = 0.471 and ARI = 0.466, and applying FCM further improved the results to NMI = 0.535, ARI = 0.572, and FPC = 0.495. Similarly, for the meta-path view, K-means achieved NMI = 0.367 and ARI = 0.287, and FCM achieved NMI = 0.468, ARI = 0.485, and FPC = 0.501, all substantially outperforming the raw-feature baselines. These results indicate that, given high-quality self-supervised embeddings, FCM can not only improve clustering performance over K-means but also produce partitions with moderate fuzziness.

Furthermore, when clustering is performed on the `concat_std` embedding obtained by view-wise standardization and concatenation of the schema and meta-path views, K-means achieves NMI = 0.567 and ARI = 0.574, and FCM achieves NMI = 0.590, ARI = 0.616, and FPC = 0.444, representing the best balance between performance and fuzziness among all settings examined in this study. Since the FPC is clearly lower than that of the individual schema and meta-path views (0.495 and 0.501), while NMI and ARI are substantially improved, we conclude that the proposed combination of view-wise standardization, concatenation, and FCM is effective for the goal of strengthening overlapping community structure while preserving a cluster structure that is highly consistent with the labels.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the proposed framework is a promising approach for analyzing embeddings learned by a self-supervised HGNN on heterogeneous graphs from the perspective of overlapping communities via fuzzy clustering.

As future work, we plan to apply the method to HINs other than DBLP and to compare it with different self-supervised HGNNs, meta-path sets, and overlapping community detection methods, in order to further clarify the generality and limitations of our approach and to connect the obtained fuzzy community structures to concrete applications such as identifying and recommending interdisciplinary researchers.

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